

The Effect of Indoor and Outdoor Physical Exercise on Physical and Psychological Wellbeing of Women

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Abstract

Regular physical activity is vital for good physical and mental health. It helps improve overall health and fitness, maintain a healthy weight, reduce the risk for many chronic diseases and promote good mental health. Although women generally tend to live longer than men, they are often in poor health. Women remain at a higher risk of non-communicable diseases especially during pregnancy and postmenopausal period. Women need to have some physical activity in order to maintain good physical and psychological health. The aim of the present investigation is to study the effect of indoor and outdoor physical exercise on physical and psychological well-being among working and non-working women. A random of 120 subjects, comprising of 60 working women and 60 non-working women, each consisting of 30 women doing indoor physical exercise and 30 women doing outdoor physical exercise were selected. The tools employed and administered were the "Psychological General Well-Being Index" (PGWBI) questionnaire developed in 1971 by Harold Dupuy and revised by Dupuy and Jhon Ware in 1984 and "Physical Wellbeing Questionnaire" formulated by the investigator. The collected data was statistically analyzed using, 't'-test and Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation. The findings of the present investigation showed that working women have better physical and psychological wellbeing than the non-working women. With regard to the type of exercise, it was found that physical wellbeing was better among women doing indoor exercise and psychological wellbeing was better among the women engaged in outdoor exercise. A positive relationship was found between physical and psychological wellbeing among the sample taken for the study.

Keywords: Women, indoor exercise, outdoor exercise, physical health, psychological wellbeing.

Introduction

According to WHO, physical activity is defined as any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that result in energy expenditure beyond resting expenditure. Exercise is a subset of physical activity that is planned, structured, repetitive and purposeful in the sense that improvement or maintenance of physical fitness is the objective.

Regular physical activity promotes growth and development and has multiple benefits for physical, mental, and psychosocial health. Specifically, physical activity reduces the risk for heart disease, diabetes mellitus, osteoporosis, high blood pressure, obesity, and

metabolic syndrome; improves various other aspects of health and fitness, including aerobic capacity, muscle and bone strength, flexibility, insulin sensitivity, and lipid profiles; and reduces stress, anxiety, and depression. Physical activity can improve mental health by decreasing and preventing conditions such as anxiety and depression, as well as improving mood and other aspects of well-being. Physical activity programming specifically designed to do so can improve psychosocial outcomes such as self-concept, social behaviors, goal orientation, and most notably self-efficacy. These attributes in turn are important determinants of current and future participation in physical activity.

For women, increasing research shows that exercise may help reduce breast cancer risk. Exercise as a means of preventing or reducing the risk of various cancers, particularly breast cancer, is important for two reasons: both the direct physical effects and the indirect effect, which is preventing or contributing to mechanisms that help prevent weight gain. Another factor women need to consider is loss of bone mass, which can lead to osteoporosis. Starting at around 30 years of age, women begin to lose bone mass. Resistance and weight training are the best, but things like walking or jogging in combination with weights are good enough. Dance, Zumba and kickboxing also help with maintaining bone mass. Exercise can also help with another cause of concern for many women: their posture. Yoga is another great weight-bearing activity as well.

Many women could benefit tremendously if they were to adopt a more active lifestyle. Health benefits from exercise include lowering the risk for cardiovascular disease, slowing the rate of bone loss in osteoporosis, and improving mood during pregnancy. Exercise is a type of physical activity that is planned and structured with the intention of improving physical fitness. An exercise prescription is a written or verbal order from a healthcare provider to a patient describing the type, duration, intensity, and frequency of exercise recommended for the patient to achieve a particular health goal.

Exercise can be either done indoors or outdoors. Indoor physical exercise is the exercise which includes strength and resistance training, which can firm, strength and tone muscles, as well as improves bone strength, balance and coordination. Example of indoor exercise of strength moves are push-ups, pull-ups, lunges and bicep curls using dumbbells. Indoor exercises also include stair climbing, elliptical trainers, indoor rower, stationary bicycle, treadmill and aerobic gymnastics.

Outdoor physical exercise is any physical activity that uses large muscle groups and causes the body to use more oxygen than it would while resting. The goal of outdoor exercise is to increase cardiovascular endurance. It increases heart rate and breathing rate by stimulating the heart and lungs to keep the body maintained during exercise. Examples of outdoor exercise include running, cycling, swimming, and brisk walking, skipping rope, rowing, hiking, playing tennis, etc. and this type of exercises require oxygenated blood to be delivered by the heart to working muscles.

Personal health is a dynamic state of human being. It is influenced by four multiple factors, such as- heredity, environment, personal behavior and access to professional health care practitioners and other health services. Good health is very much important for normal works in daily life and also for professional works. Each group of women has different life style and workloads for which they might have different fitness level as well as different health status.

The globalization and especially technological transformation has opened door for women to new opportunities in their work life. Now, women take part in all the occupations and professions, which were done only by men earlier. The role conflict and dual role of working women has resulted in stress, tension, anxiety, obesity, etc and consequently, working women are facing frequent ill health, both psychological and physical.

Exercising plays a vital role and helps women not only to be physically fit but also improves their mental health. According to Anxiety and Depression Association America, exercise is also

considered vital for maintaining mental fitness, and it can reduce stress. Studies show exercise is very effective at reducing fatigue, improving alertness and concentration, and at enhancing overall cognitive function. Science has also provided some evidence that physically active people have lower rates of anxiety and depression than sedentary people. Exercise may improve mental health by helping the brain cope better with stress.

According to WHO, physical activity has also been associated with improved psychological health by reducing levels of stress, anxiety and depression. This is particularly important for women who demonstrate an incidence of depression that is reported to be almost double that of men in both developed and developing countries. It has also been suggested that physical activity can contribute to building self-esteem and confidence and can provide a vehicle for social integration and equality for women in society.

Despite this, physical inactivity is generally more prevalent among girls and women than their male counterparts in India. There are many barriers for women which is the cause of this physical inactivity. Some obstacles include taking care of children, lack of time and motivation, taking care of elderly, unable to travel to health centers or physical activity facilities due to limited mobility and cultural expectations.

Exercising on regular basis has been proven to lower the risk of physical and psychological health problems. However, there is still more to be known about the effects of indoor and outdoor exercise on womens' well-being. This paper will hopefully bridge the gap between wellbeing and physical exercise.

Literature Review

To find out the research gap, few of the secondary literature was searched and reviewed chronologically as under.

Mishra (2004) studied on Yoga for body image and self concept in varsity of women. In a time series experiment, fifty (n=50) young women age 20-24 years, participated actively. This was a longitudinal study conducted for a period of two years. Pretest, posttest, and follow up tests on self concept and body image were conducted after a yoga training intervention for three months in first year, where the follow up was continued in second year. The result of t-test revealed that yoga practices have a definite impact on own body image and self concept in varsity of women.

Exercise can also have an impact on the mental a wellbeing. McInman and Berger (2007) studied on the self-concept and mood changes associated with aerobic dance. The sample size of the study consists of female aerobic dance participants and female university students. Analyses revealed significant positive changes for aerobic dance participants on specific dimensions of mood, whereas controls showed minimal changes .

Marandi, et al. (2008) examined the effects of light and moderate aerobic intensity on body composition and serum lipid profile in obese/overweight women. Forty-five middle-aged obese/overweight volunteer women (25-40 years, and body mass index (BMI) ≥ 25 to 30 kg/m²) were randomly assigned into three groups: 1) Light aerobics, 2) Moderate aerobics, 3) No exercise training (control). The intensity of aerobics was controlled by monitoring heart rate. Body composition was measured using skin fold thickness method. Serum lipid was measured. The results showed that both light and moderate aerobics improved body composition and serum lipid profile in obese/overweight women.

In recent years young girls lack physical activity which leads to increased health risks in this age group. Kemp and Pienaa (2009) studied on the decreasing tendencies of physical activity among adolescent girls. The result of the study stated that an aerobic based exercise programme, conducted in a playful and enjoyable manner and according to guidelines set for health enhancement, can improve aerobic endurance, leading to increased physical activity among girls in their teenage years.

Many women prefer to do indoor exercise. Rogerson (2015) studied the influences of green outdoors versus indoors environmental settings on psychological and social outcomes of controlled exercise, and concluded that exercise in a natural environment may promote directed attention and social interactions, which may positively influence future exercise intentions. Similarly the results of a study conducted by Fannon (2015) concluded that exercising in a green outdoor environment has been shown to have psychological and physiological benefits when compared to indoor, or non-green, exercise environments.

The literature review clearly indicates that any kind of physical exercise is beneficial for physical and psychological health. However, there is still more to be known about the effects of indoor and outdoor exercise. Though many studies have been carried out in western countries, research in this field is relatively scarce in India and almost negligible effort has been taken among Indian women. Hence, to bridge this research gap, this study on the effect of indoor and outdoor physical exercise on physical and psychological wellbeing of women has been conducted.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the effect of indoor physical exercise on physical and psychological well-being among working and non-working women.
- To study the effect of outdoor physical exercise on physical and psychological well-being among working and non-working women.
- To study the relationship between physical and psychological well-being among working and non-working women.

Methodology

The sample for the present study was selected by random sampling method. A total sample of 120 subjects, comprising of 60 working women and 60 non-working women, each consisting of 30 women doing indoor physical exercise and 30 women doing outdoor physical exercise were selected.

“Physical Well-Being Questionnaire” formulated by the investigator was used to determine the physical wellbeing of the chosen women. The “Psychological General Well-Being Index” (PGWBI) questionnaire was used to assess the psychological wellbeing of the sample. Developed in 1971 by Harold Dupuy and revised by Dupuy and John Ware in 1984, this questionnaire, is one of the most widely used instruments for evaluating a person’s psychological well-being and has been translated into many languages worldwide. The collected data was statistically analyzed by mean, standard deviation, ‘t’-test and Karl Pearson’s coefficient of correlation.

Results and Discussion

The results of this study on the effect of indoor and outdoor physical exercise on physical and psychological wellbeing among women are presented here.

The result of ‘t’ test computed to find out the difference in physical wellbeing between working and non-working women is presented in table-1.

Table 1 Comparison of physical wellbeing between working and non- working women doing outdoor exercise

Variable	Working status	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	't' Value	Level of Significance
Physical wellbeing	Working	30	63.53	9.66	2.41	0.05
	Non-working	30	58.47	6.27		

From the result presented in table-1, it is evident that there is a significant difference in the physical wellbeing of working and non-working women doing outdoor exercise as the calculated 't' value 2.41 is above the table value 1.93 at 5% level of significance. From the mean value which is 63.53 for working women and 58.47 for non-working women, we can infer that among the women doing outdoor exercise the working women have better physical health than non-working women.

The following table provide details of 't' test computed to find out the difference in physical wellbeing between women doing indoor and outdoor exercise.

Table 2 Comparison of physical wellbeing between non-working women doing indoor and outdoor exercise

Variable	Type of exercise	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	't' value	Level of Significance
Physical wellbeing	Indoor	30	65.37	12.53	2.69	0.01
	Outdoor	30	58.47	6.27		

Analysis of table-2 shows that there is a significant difference in the physical wellbeing between non-working women doing indoor and outdoor exercise as the calculated 't' value 2.69 is above the table value 2.58 at 1% level of significance. The mean physical wellbeing score for non-working women doing indoor exercise is 65.37 and for those doing outdoor exercise it is 58.47. This clearly shows that non-working women doing indoor exercise enjoy better physical wellbeing than the women doing outdoor exercise.

The result of 't' test computed to find out the difference in psychological wellbeing between working and non-working women is presented in table-3.

Table 3 Comparison of psychological wellbeing between working and non- working women doing indoor exercise

Variable	Working status	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	't' value	Level of Significance
Psychological wellbeing	Working	30	58.63	7.73	2.33	0.05
	Non-working	30	53.73	8.57		

The results portrayed in table-3 shows that there is a significant difference in the psychological wellbeing of working and non-working women doing indoor exercise as the calculated 't' value 2.33 is above the table value 1.93 at 5% level of significance. From the mean value which is 58.63 for working women and 53.73 for non-working women, we can infer that the working women have better psychological wellbeing than non-working women who do indoor exercise.

This result is supported by a study conducted by Sinha (2017) who concluded that employed

women are more satisfied with their life than nonworking women, and the quality of home and work environments determines the impact of employment on the psychological well-being of working women in dual-earner families.

The following table provide details of ‘t’ test computed to find out the difference in psychological wellbeing between women doing indoor and outdoor exercise

Table 4 Comparison of psychological wellbeing between women doing indoor and outdoor exercise

Variable	Type of exercise	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	‘t’ value	Level of Significance
Psychological wellbeing	Indoor	60	56.18	8.46	1.99	0.05
	Outdoor	60	59.63	10.36		

From table-4 it is evident that there is a significant difference in the psychological wellbeing of women doing indoor and outdoor exercise as the calculated ‘t’ value 1.99 is above the table value 1.93 at 5% level of significance. The mean psychological wellbeing score for women doing indoor exercise is 56.18 and for those doing outdoor exercise it is 59.63. This clearly shows that women doing outdoor exercise have better psychological wellbeing than the women doing indoor exercise.

This finding is substantiated by the results of a study conducted Hooper (2013) who investigated indoor and outdoor exercise environments and their effect on mood states, heart rate, and running time. The author concluded that when an exercise environment is perceived positively, mood states will be affected more positively than when an exercise environment is perceived less favorably.

Mental disorders are of major public health significance. It has been claimed that vigorous physical activity has positive effects on mental health in both clinical and nonclinical populations. The result of the correlation analysis carried out to find the relationship between physical wellbeing and psychological wellbeing is presented in table 5.

Table 5 Relationship between physical wellbeing and psychological wellbeing

Variables	Psychological wellbeing	Level of Significance
Physical wellbeing	0.69	0.01

It is observed from table 5 that there exists a positive correlation between physical wellbeing and psychological wellbeing at 1% level as the correlation score was found to be 0.696. This result clearly indicates that good physical health promotes psychological wellbeing.

This result is substantiated by a study conducted by Taylor, Sallis and Needle (1985) who investigated the relation of physical activity and exercise to mental health and found that exercise helps alleviate some symptoms associated with mild to moderate depression. The evidence also suggests that physical activity and exercise might alter aspects of coronary-prone (Type A) behavior and physiological response to stressors.

Conclulsion

- Working women doing outdoor exercise have better physical health and psychological wellbeing than the non-working women.
- Physical wellbeing was better among those doing indoor exercise especially among non-working women.
- It was found that women who do outdoor exercise have better psychological wellbeing.
- A positive relationship was observed between physical wellbeing and psychological wellbeing.

Scope for Further Study

1. A cross cultural study can be conducted with a larger sample size.
2. Comparison can be done based on gender
3. Comparison can be done based on age group
4. A comparative study can be carried out between women doing and not doing exercise.

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